

DLR AS THE TOOL FOR PROVIDING FLEXIBILITY SERVICES IN THE DISTRIBUTION NETWORK

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ABSTRACT

The paper describes the use of dynamic line rating (DLR) as a tool for providing flexibility in the power system, specifically for power transfer. The flexibility service can be offered to large wind farm (WF) energy producers by distributed system operators (DSO). The dynamic load capacity of the line, which varies depending on weather conditions, is utilized to provide flexibility services.

The paper describes the use of this property within a designed market of flexibility services. The basic principles of calculating the dynamic load capacity of lines based on weather forecasts and the use of these results for optimal power generation from renewable sources, particularly large WF directly connected to the 110 kV network, are presented. The calculated hourly profiles of the permissible forecast load on the line enable the provision of flexibility services related to the management of limitations caused by the risk of exceeding limit values and permissible temperature values of the line conductor. An example of implementation as part of the demonstration installation of the Horizon 2020 EUniversal project is provided, describing the entire process of field implementation. The flexibility service will be provided to those 110 kV lines that are related to power transfer from large wind farms. The critical spans of these lines, i.e. those for which there is a risk of failure to keep the permissible wire distance from the ground, are selected based on data from airborne inspection of the lines and laser scanning longitudinal HV line profile.

INTRODUCTION

The flexibility of a power system refers to its ability to adapt to changes in demand and generation in a way that ensures the security of energy supply and optimal utilization of energy sources, particularly renewable sources. [1]

In a centralized system, where sources with planned and stable generation play a dominant role, this requirement is typically done using a power system frequency controller, Central Power and Frequency Control (CPFC), which adjusts the output of generators in response to changes in demand or supply.

However, as the energy system shifts towards decentralization and greater reliance on renewable sources, a more flexible and intelligent system is required, utilizing consumer participation, improved

interconnection, more efficient large-scale energy storage, and demand response and management utilizing digital technologies [2]

Managing such a system, in addition to the active participation of consumers and energy producers, requires the implementation of new services and products. One such service is the flexibility service, which can be offered on the planned flexibility services market by both system operators and energy producers [3]. Flexibility services offered may concern both dynamically changing conditions of energy transmission through network elements and adaptation of energy production to current needs.

The Congestion Management Service (CMS) is a flexibility service that addresses constraints imposed by thermal, voltage, and stability limit violations on network elements such as transmission lines, cables, and transformers [4]. Its purpose is to mitigate the risk of boundary violations and restore the network to within acceptable operational limits.

WHAT IS DYNAMIC LINE RATING

In recent years, there has been an increase in the number of unpredictable events in power transmission and distribution systems. This is due to a variety of factors, including known causes of uncertainty such as weather phenomena (e.g. hurricanes, extreme temperatures, snowfall, and icing), as well as new factors related to human activity such as the integration of variable renewable generation and the use of special devices (such as FACTS and UPFC) to direct power flow according to commercial requirements. As a result, it has become increasingly difficult to accurately predict and manage power systems in the short term, which can lead to errors in power system management. To mitigate these errors and ensure the reliable and stable operation of the power system, it is necessary to implement measures that can reduce their impact.

One of the basic conditions for the safe operation of a power line is to maintain a safe distance from the ground and objects located under the high-voltage (HV) line. This distance depends on objects specified in applicable standard [5] and, for a line with a nominal voltage of 110 kV, this distance from the ground surface should be 5.85 meters.

The technical implementation of this requirement involves determining the maximum current that, flowing through the line under the weather conditions assumed for the calculations, will not cause unacceptable proximity to objects under the line. The current thus determined is called the dynamic line current to emphasize that its value changes with changing weather conditions [6].

The line load capacity refers to the amount of electrical power that a transmission line can safely carry.

To determine the line load capacity, it is necessary to consider the type and size of the phase conductor, as well as the topographic data of the line such as its location, critical spans, and height above the ground. One method of determining the permissible load capacity is to use forecasts of weather conditions to calculate the spatial location of the cable in the span. This approach is different from others that rely on measurements of conductor parameters, such as temperature, tension, angle of inclination, or vibration frequency. The use of dynamic line load capacity in distribution networks can help to utilize the transmission capacity of the line more effectively. For example, for a wind speed of 6 m/s blowing perpendicular to the line, the load capacity of the line increases by 50% compared to the wind of 0.5 m/s. Permissible line load calculations are made using CIGRE recommended line thermal model based on the heat balance between cooling and heating of the line in static conditions (1).

$$P_J + P_S = P_C + P_r \quad (1)$$

where:

Heating: P_J = due to current flow (Joule heat)

P_S = solar heating

Cooling: P_C = by convection

P_r = by radiation

Figure 1. Line thermal model with the objective function: heat balance

The same mathematical model is used to calculate the permissible line load in the forecasted weather conditions [7].

In the equations describing these components of the heat balance (Figure 1), there are variables related to weather values (outdoor temperature T_a , solar irradiation S , wind speed and direction), a variable representing the root mean square (RMS) value of the flowing current and constant values describing the properties of the conductor material. The model also considers the thermal absorption coefficient of the wire surface α_s used to determine solar heating P_S and the thermal emission coefficient of the wire surface ϵ used to determine cooling by radiation P_r .

USE CASE

As part of the demonstration implementation of the Horizon 2020 EUniversal project, tests were conducted related to the provision of the flexibility service for a select number of 110 kV lines (Figure 2), concerning the forecasted energy delivery from large wind farms located in the north of Poland. Table 1 lists the names of the wind farms and their generation power as specified in the connection agreement with the DSO, as well as the nominal (rated) power which, in some cases, may be generated after obtaining the required permission from the DSO. The difference between the nominal and connection power may be considered as the power that can be generated if the line's capacity allows for it. This surplus of generation power, after calculation of the allowable dynamic line capacity, may be offered as a flexibility service by the line owner, i.e., the DSO. Wind Farms are flexibility services buyers entitled to issue a buy order.

Table 1 List of the Wind Farms

Pos	WF name abbreviation	Generation power [MW]	
		Connection	Nominal
1	KKA	46	52,9
2	KC]	51	51
3	BSK	12,5	15
4	SSL	19,2	23,4
5	TYM	48,0	48

Table 2 shows the lines to which wind farms are connected (directly or indirectly) and whose permissible load capacity may, under certain conditions, limit the size of power generation from wind farms. These limitations result from the risk of failure to keep the permissible distance from the wire to the ground in the spans called critical spans.

Selection of critical spans requires knowledge of the construction data of all spans of the line, such as the length of the span, and suspension height of the lowest phase wire above the ground. These data can be obtained from airborne inspection or HV line passports.

In Table 2 the critical spans data of the selected lines are presented, such as distance to the ground at a specified temperature. Line numbers in Table 2 correspond to the line numbers depicted in Figure 2.

Figure 2. SCADA screenshot of the part of the 110 kV network under test.

Table 2. Lines and critical span data

Line No	Line name abbrev	Span No	Distance to ground [m]	Wire temp [C deg]	Lengths [m]	Wire type
1	DUN-PNO	15-16	6,8	80	285	AFL-6 240
2	PNO-USM	91-92	6,6	80	264	AFL-6 240
3	USM-KKA	25-26	6,7	35	230	AFL-6 240
4	KKA-KOK	48-49	6,4	14,2	201	AFL-6 240
5	KOK-KLG	12-13	6,9	14	278	AFL-6 240
6	KLK-KCO	18-19	8,2	12	237	GAP GTACSR 150
7	KCO-TBT	63-64	8,1	10,6	259	GAP GTACSR 150

The forecasted allowable hourly load profile is calculated for all 110 kV lines managed by the Energa-Opertaor (DSO) and used in the congestion management calculation program. The calculation process starts with a resolution that is adjusted to the weather forecast update cycle (6 hours) and the time range of the hourly profile of the permissible load is 72 hours. The main steps of the calculation process are:

1. Reading input data such as mechanical data of critical line spans: span, cable attachment point height on both sides of the span, cable characteristics (diameter, cable type, cooling/heating factors) and cable initial stress.
2. Selection of the weather forecast appropriate for the location of the critical span of the line.
3. Calculation of the permissible load in the forecasted weather conditions using the thermal model of the line following the CIGRE recommendations.
4. Transfer of calculation results to the SCADA Syndis AMS system for use by the program for calculating the flow in the 110 kV network, considering the determined permissible line loads.

5. Finally, allowable Wind Farm generation is calculated

The process of handling the wind farm producer's notification of the intention to produce energy over the contractual conditions is supported by a dedicated cooperation module with the NODES service platform used within Euniversal project. Universal Market Enabling Interface (UMEI), built as part of the project, is used for information exchange.

The algorithm was tested using real energy generation data from two wind farms over 8 hours of high generation (27.12.2022 09:00 to 27.12.2022 17:00).

Low temperatures did not pose limitations on allowable line power capacity, so weather data from a hot summer day was used for the test purpose as the base for DLR allowable line capacity in the region. Results of the calculation for line 4 KKA-KOK are shown in Figure 3. Table 3 presents generation values for two WF (KKA and KCO) resulting from their hourly forecast and values that may be introduced to the grid due to line load limitations calculated by the power flow software.

Table 3 also shows the permissible line load (DLR limit) for each line and the power flow at the two WF generation values (forecasted and allowed). Results marked in the table as "forecast/allowed" are the line power flows which correspond to these two generation values.

For some hours, line power flow equal to the DLR limit introduces the curtailment in forecasted WF generation marked in Table 3 in red.

Figure 3. DLR calculation results for the line 4 KKA-KOK

Table 3 Forecasted line capacity vs forecasted WF generation

time	Wind Farm generation				Line power flow [MW]					
	KKA		KCO		L3 USM- KKA		L4- KKA-KOK		L 5- KOK-KLG	
	forecast	allowed	forecast	allowed	DLR limit	forecast/ allowed	DLR limit	forecast/ allowed	DLR limit	forecast/ allowed
9:00	49,2	46,0	52,9	47,9	69,1	58,2/60,7	33,2	35/33,2	30,7	25,1/24,1
10:00	47,9	46,0	55,6	45,6	68,5	56,8/58,7	32,9	34/32,9	30,9	25,2/24,2
11:00	47,1	46,0	52,8	47,8	67,6	58,2/61,4	32,4	35/32,4	29,6	24,9/23,9
12:00	46,9	46,0	51,2	47,2	66,1	57,8/61,5	31,7	35/31,7	26,5	23,5/23,1
13:00	46,0	46	48	47,1	65,7	57,7/61,6	31,5	34/31,5	30,7	26,2/25,6
14:00	45,0	45	47	46	64,5	56,4/60,0	31,0	36/31,0	30,1	25,8/24,3
15:00	46,9	46,0	51,2	50,3	66,2	59,7/64,5	31,8	36/31,8	30,8	26,4/24,8
16:00	46,1	46,0	50	50	65,3	59,5/64,7	31,3	36/31,3	31,2	27,1/24,3
17:00	45,0	45,0	49	48,7	64,0	58,1/63,0	30,7	35/30,7	29,4	26,5/24,2

CONCLUSIONS

The use of determining the dynamic load capacity of lines described in the article to manage congestion and provide flexibility services will allow for achieving such benefits as preventing grid overloads, especially lines, improving the quality of energy supply or limiting or postponing network investments.

Managing constraints and offering renewable energy producers the flexibility of the distribution network using

forecasts of the dynamic load capacity of 110 kV lines is already possible in most DSOs in Poland (Energia, ENEA, Tauron, PGE - some branches) in which systems for monitoring the permissible line load capacity (systems DOL) using the measurement of weather conditions. For this purpose, the mechanical data of the line already existing in the system and the same algorithm for determining the dynamic load capacity of the line would be used, with the measurement data of weather conditions replaced with forecasted values.

The use of DOL to manage the generation of wind farms is particularly effective when the wind farms, taking advantage of good wind conditions, operate with power close to the rated power and at the same time the transmission line wires are cooled more intensively than in calm weather.

Implementation of congestion management with the use of dynamic line load capacity enables technical and cost-effectively ensure safe operation of the distribution system both under current operating conditions and for expected (forecasted) conditions [9]. The use of the dynamic line load capacity in the operation of the distribution network leads to better and more effective use of the transmission capacity of the line.

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